

Scientific article

An approximation of the optimal combined helix and yaw control for wind farm co-design applications

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Abstract: *Different wind farm flow control strategies have recently been proposed to maximize the energy production of a wind farm. To assess the benefits of these strategies, a computationally demanding optimization problem is solved to determine the optimal control settings of each turbine for all flow cases. This work introduces novel analytical methods to approximate these optimal settings for three control strategies, namely wake steering, helix, and a combined strategy between these two techniques, for different degrees of wind direction uncertainty. This method is referred to as geometric wind farm control and enables a fast assessment of the effect of these strategies, avoiding the need for optimization. Our results show that the root mean square error between the optimal and geometric values is below 3.6° and 1.6° for yaw and helix amplitude, respectively. Using these geometric approximations, wind farm control co-design problems become tractable, as they allow the integration of wind farm control into layout optimization while maintaining the dimensionality of the problem.*

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